

BUDAPEST UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AND ECONOMICS
FACULTY OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
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Applicability of gamma irradiation for the production of UHMWPE composites for joint implant inserts

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About implants

- **Inserts** made of **UHMWPE** by **sintering**
 - Extremely long molecular chain
 - Inert
 - Excellent tribological and sliding properties
- Final shape is formed by **machining**

Insert manufacturing technology

Schematic of a ram extruder

Kurtz S. M.: UHMWPE
Biomaterials
handbook (2015)

Typical implant design

About implants

- Most commonly used **sliding pair** is **metal-polymer**
- Most common **reasons for revision** is the **failure of inserts**

Distribution of sliding pairs by material

István Nemes-Károly,
 Gábor Szabéni:
 Improving Optical Damage
 Analysis of Knee Implants
 from an Engineering
 Perspective, Periodica
 Polytechnica Mechanical
 Engineering 67 (2), 151-
 160 (2023)

Kurtz S. M.: UHMWPE
 Biomaterials
 handbook (2015)

<i>Anatomical design (TSA)</i>	<i>Reverse design (TSA)</i>
Glenoid loosening	Scapula notching
Instability	Glenoid complications
Rotator cuff tear	Hematoma
Periprosthetic bone fracture	Instability
Infection	Infection
Neural injuries	Neurological complications
Prosthesis wear	Humeral complications

7 most common reasons for revision surgery

Broken inserts and image from 3D scanner

Self-reinforced

Self-reinforcing composite:

- **Surface of reinforcing structure melts, will retain its orientation**
- More than **90%** of the **tensile strength** of the fibers is **retained**
- **Avoidable adhesion problems** (polyolefin)
- **Materials:**
 - **GUR 1020** matrix (typical insert material)
 - **Dyneema Purity** fiber (2006-sewing material)
 - **Medical grade materials**

Matrix powder (GUR 1020) and fiber (Dyneema)

Cryogenic grinder

DSC measurement:

- Theoretically **10 °C higher melting point for fibers**
 - Actually **~6.6 °C**
- Theoretically **irradiation increases the melting point of fibers**
 - Effect of **irradiation on fibers** is a **decrease in melting point**
- **Irradiation of the finished self-reinforced composite**

DSC measurement
(10 °C/min heating rate)

Sintering

After long series of iterations, the technology has been adjusted:

- Excessively harsh temperatures melt fibers
- Too low temperature not enough to consolidate constituents

Electron microscope image (fiber)

Testing of composites

- Shore hardness test
- Pin-on-disc tribometer (POD) test:
 - For **wear testing**:
 - Alternating movement (8 hours, 15 N)
 - Without lubrication
 - **Bovine serum** lubrication
 - Examination of **wear marks** using **confocal, optical and electron microscopy**
- Wettability testing

Pin-on-disc tribometer

VR microscopic image of wear mark

Wettability test

- Shore hardness test:
 - No significant difference
 - **Matrix material dominates**
 - **Minimal hardening due to post-irradiation**

■ Unirradiated
■ 200 kGy irradiated fiber
■ 80 kGy irradiated fiber
■ 80 kGy irradiated composite

- POD test:
 - Friction coefficient increases with fiber content
 - Technology is **not reliable** for fibers irradiated with 200 kGy

Dynamic friction coefficient without lubrication

Static friction coefficient without lubrication

- POD test:

- **Dynamic friction coefficient decreases due to fiber content**

- **Static friction coefficient initially increases, then remains unchanged due to the effect of the fiber content**

Dynamic friction coefficient with lubrication

Static friction coefficient with lubrication

- POD test:
 - **Without lubrication**, minimal wear ~50%
 - **With lubrication**, minimal wear ~25%
 - **Higher fiber content**, **pitting**, **rigid** behavior
- Wettability test:
 - **Irradiated fiber reduces wettability**

- POD test:
 - Friction coefficient increases due to post-irradiation

Dynamic friction coefficient without lubrication

Static friction coefficient without lubrication

- POD test:
 - Friction coefficient increases due to post-irradiation
 - Minor change in friction coefficient when lubricated

Dynamic friction coefficient with lubrication

Static friction coefficient with lubrication

- POD test:
 - **Post-irradiation improves wear resistance**
 - **Higher fiber content, pitting, rigid behavior**
 - **Post-irradiation causes pitting, rigid behavior**
- Wettability test:
 - **Post-irradiation reduces wettability**

- Microscopic test:
 - Pitting
 - Rigid behavior

Ductile behavior

Rigid behavior

Summary

- **Not worth** using irradiated fiber
- **Friction coefficient increases** with fiber content and **post-irradiation**
- **Post-irradiation** and **higher fiber content** causes **pitting**, rigid behavior
- **Irradiated fiber** and **post-irradiation** reduces **wettability**
- **Tasks to be solved:**
 - Improve **dispersion of fibers**
 - Development of **softening heat treatment**
 - **Testing** samples in multi-axis **joint simulator**

Multi-axis joint simulator

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